

IT SECTOR BUSINESS TRENDS AND SPECIFIC IT PROJECTS**Denić N.***Faculty of Sciences and Mathematics
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In this research paper, based on a studios review of the relevant scientific literature and conducted research in practice, the results of the state of IT business and development trends in the Republic of Serbia will be presented. At the beginning of the work, the latest scientific literature in the field of digital transformations, information technologies and project management of the implementation of IT projects will be developed. In the theoretical part, in addition to the above, the specifics of IT projects will be analyzed, the division of IT projects will be defined. In this context, the paradox of the lack of qualified workforce in the field of IT on the one hand, and the appearance of mass layoffs of IT experts and the demand for employment on the other hand, will be evolved. The paper will present the theoretical foundations of IT project management through the concept of the project triangle, that is, the identification of key success factors for the introduction of these projects in companies. Also, the paper will investigate possible current trends and future perspectives of the situation on the labor market of IT experts from the aspect of personal income in the conditions of the current economic crisis in the world caused by increased energy prices. In this context, the paper will present the results of research into the state of business results of companies in the Republic of Serbia, then the state of the workforce in the field of IT, with a comparison of the state in EU member states, where the results and different levels of development of individual countries in the field of the IT sector and digital transformation will be presented. In the final part of the work, the perspective will be analyzed and the possible impacts of new technologies will be examined with a special emphasis on the impact of artificial intelligence on the reduction of jobs, changes in the way of doing business and the emergence of new professions.

Keywords: IT sector, Management project, IT project.

INTRODUCTION

In the turbulent economic conditions of business caused by wars, the economic and energy crisis and contradictions, the lack of quality and trained workforce is increasingly pronounced[6]. In this regard, according to Eurostat data for 2024, as many as 57.5% of companies in the EU fail to find enough qualified IT experts. Data for the Republic of Serbia show that the domestic industry currently lacks more than 30,000 trained experts, so that in the long term this can significantly slow down the growth of the economy. In terms of economic activities, the IT sector remained one of

the most important exporters of services from Serbia in 2025, with a continuation of the growth trend, a stable inflow of foreign currency and a realized foreign trade deficit. However, like others, this industry is also facing a series of structural problems that are increasingly openly questioning its medium-term development potential. In this context, according to research, large companies have the biggest problems with the lack of qualified IT experts - 68% of them cannot fill all IT positions, while challenges are also present in medium-sized (59.2%) and small companies (53.4%). In the education system of the Republic of Serbia, in the state

and private sector, there are quite a number of study programs for educating personnel in the field of IT, however, there is still a demand for this type of personnel on the labor market[7]. Another problem that occurs in the sphere of the IT sector is the shutdown of several large IT companies in Serbia, which left hundreds of people without work in a short period of time and opened some new questions about the impact of new technologies and artificial intelligence, the stability of the business environment and the long-term sustainability of the domestic IT model. The state of the IT sector in the world is such that, according to the data of the TrueUp platform, during 2025, around 245,000 layoffs were recorded in the technology sector worldwide, while in the first months of 2026, around 94,000 employees in almost 240 companies remained without work. This is also indicated by the fact that the co-founder of the global IT company "Block" Jack Dorsey explained the dismissal of 40 percent of employees by claiming that AI tools can work more, better and faster because it is the most transformative technology we have seen since the Internet. The aforementioned trend in the world has not bypassed Serbia either, the wave of layoffs that has affected the global IT industry has also reached Serbia, but experts warn that it is not a crisis, but a deep transformation of the labor market in which artificial intelligence, changed business models and increasingly fierce competition are changing the existing and setting new rules of the game. The latest research and estimates by the Serbian IT Association (SITA) show that between 70,000 and 80,000 workers are employed in key IT activities in Serbia. In this context, the latest layoffs in the IT sector do not sound like a good indicator for this year and the development of the domestic IT industry, which has definitely been one of the more potent export-oriented branches of the Republic of Serbia's economy for years. Many companies and business systems in Serbia were affected by the lack of work on the global market or problems in specific industries, which resulted in a decrease in income and in some cases led to the decision to lay off a large number of employees[8]. However, in spite of the mentioned problems, the office for information technologies and electronic administration announced that at the end of the third quarter of 2025 in the entire ICT sector. 115,933 people worked, which is 3,678 or 3.3 percent more compared to the same quarter of the previous year. Regarding the situation in the environment, the greatest demand for IT personnel is in Germany, the Czech Republic, Malta, Austria and Luxembourg, where more than 65% of companies fail to find adequate candidates. However, on the other hand, in support of the lack of IT personnel in large companies, the numbers speak for themselves - for example, in Malta as many as 84% of large companies have a problem with hiring IT experts, in Germany 80%, while similar trends apply to the Czech Republic (79%), Slovenia (78%), Austria (76%) and Luxembourg (75%). In contrast, the results show that in the Republic of Serbia last year, the number of people who lost their jobs in the IT sector is estimated between 450 and 550, which is one of the most pronounced waves of layoffs in the domestic IT sector in the last few years. In addition to the fact that the salaries of IT experts are high according to the

data of the Republic Institute of Statistics for the year 2024, the sector of computer programming and related services records an average net salary of RSD 282,510 (about €2,400 per month). In practice, there are noticeable contradictions, i.e. the paradox that despite the obvious demand for personnel in the IT profession, some employers from this branch state that as many as 2,500 applications are received for one job advertisement in the IT industry in Serbia.

2.SPECIFIC IT PROJECTS

Poslovanje u IT sektoru je usko povezano sa IT projektima stim u vezi u nastavku su date neke od specifičnosti projekata sa akcentom na IT projektima. U literaturi se navodi model tkz. projektnog trougla koji naglašava tri fundamentalna ograničenja koja oblikuju svaki pa i IT projekat: obim posla, vremenski okvir i raspoloživi resursi [14].

Fig. 1. Project triangle [14]

In the context of IT project management, the constraints are often illustrated by the aforementioned "project management triangle" concept. As explained by (Nizhebetskyi, 2022), the essence of the project triangle is to balance these constraints in order to achieve the best possible result or quality [14]. Practice shows that all projects have a beginning and an end. In addition, they have a team, a budget, a schedule, and a set of expectations that the team must meet. According to the well-known institute, each project is unique and differs from routine operations (current activities of the organization) because projects end when the goal is achieved [16]. In general, it can be said that all projects are temporary endeavors to create value through a unique product, service or result.

According to the relevant literature, IT projects can be divided into the following eight categories [2]:

1. Software development
2. Web development
3. Application of technology
4. Cloud computing
5. Maintenance and support
7. Cyber security
8. Training

3. IT PROJECT MANAGEMENT

IT project management is the application of processes, methods, skills, knowledge and experience to achieve specific project goals in accordance with project acceptance criteria within agreed parameters. A well-known author states that the use of IT project management provides companies with benefits such as [17]: better control of financial, physical and human resources; improved customer relations; shorter development time; lower costs; higher quality and higher reliability; higher profit margins; improved productivity; better internal coordination and greater employee motivation. IT project management has end results that are limited by time frame and budget [1]. According to well-known authors, IT project management is used in

all areas of activity and business processes, including companies with a process-oriented production system [13]. It is known that IT project management is defined as the process of project management from the beginning through its life cycle. The primary goal of IT project management is to complete the project within the established time, budget and quality objectives[12].

IT project management is the discipline of applying established principles, procedures and policies for successful project management from conception to completion. The literature states that IT project management requires the application of these principles and procedures, as well as tools and technologies, to ensure that the project can be completed in a way that meets all articulated outcomes - from cost constraints to ultimate goals[15]. For an IT project to be successful, it must effectively meet certain criteria. In this context, some authors point out that it is quite possible for the project to be completed on time and within the budget, but still fail if it does not meet the client's expectations [18]. While other authors emphasize that the implementation of a realistic analysis of costs and benefits additionally increases the probability of achieving customer satisfaction and providing measurable business benefits [10]. Also very important is the understanding of customer requirements, which includes two key components: examining the customer's needs and validating the team's understanding[4]. In theory and practice, various frameworks, methods and practices have developed over time to support agile project management. In this regard, the renowned institution PMI lists Scrum, Kanban, Scrumban, Extreme Programming (XP), Crystal, Feature-Driven Development (FDD), DSDM, SAFe® and LeSS among the most common[16]. According to the report on the state of agile development, Scrum remains the dominant approach, used by 87% of respondents, followed by Kanban (56%), Scrumban (27%), iterative methods (20%) and Scrum/XP hybrids (13%) [9].

In this sense, with regard to the success of the introduction of IT projects, the well-known authors Irijarte and Bayona (2020) based on the results of their research identify the following factors as key to the success of an IT project[11]: customer satisfaction, user satisfaction, compliance with the budget, compliance with the schedule, quality of information, efficiency of the process, quality of the system, understanding of needs, creation of business value, competitive advantages, satisfaction of contractors, duration, efficient performance of tasks, financial budget, functionality, achievement of goals, individual influence, effectiveness of leadership, fulfillment of functional requirements, fulfillment of non-functional requirements, operational quality, organizational impact, final product utilization, productivity improvement, project stakeholder satisfaction, quality, quality of project management process, development team accepts requirements as realistic/achievable, resource savings, scope, quality of service, system utilization, team satisfaction, ability to achieve project goals, expected scope of work performed, project well planned, quality of work performed, project plan exists, and specifications. In addition to the above, the literature states that other important factors include supporting broader, implicit

project goals, achieving a satisfactory internal rate of return, and ensuring that each IT initiative contributes significantly to the organization's success [3].

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the research purposes of this paper, a combined qualitative-quantitative research method will be applied, which includes all modern methods and techniques of scientific research. At the beginning of the research, we first briefly defined the basic problem that we are researching or dealing with in the research. In this sense, a methodological research framework is proposed that combines different research methods, including quantitative and qualitative research methods. In the theoretical discussion, an overview or presentation of the contents researched by well-known authors in the country and abroad in the context of this topic is given. The research instruments used in the research process and procedure are: different types of questionnaires, there are tables, reviews, checks of individual and team abilities and knowledge; numerical chart and scale; special and Internet search questionnaires, etc.

5. RESULTS

The results show that in 2024, the total export of IT services in the Republic of Serbia amounted to 4.1 billion euros. Regarding the type of software services in Serbia, outsourcing is one of the dominant business models in the IT industry, which means that most software companies work on projects for foreign clients, most often from the USA, Great Britain, Germany and the EU, developing software or providing other IT services for them. In this context, when the entire domestic IT industry is observed, its total revenues amounted to 5,498,403,477 euros in 2024. This represents a growth of 13.5 percent compared to 4,843,484,596 euros recorded a year earlier. Also, the total profit in 2024 amounted to 319,390,317 euros, with an annual growth of 19.3 percent (267,496,512 euros in 2023). Taking all this into account, the results in practice indicate that companies are facing many challenges, but also new opportunities for business improvement. Regarding the location of workplaces, the research results show that the percentage of companies that work entirely from the office is on the rise compared to last year (from 7% to 13%). At the same time, in this sense, the share of the structured hybrid model is also growing (from 21% to 27%), whereby the arrangement of three days in the office per week is currently the most common. One of the key problems of the IT sector in Serbia is the strong cooling of the global IT market, especially in the segments of custom software development and outsourcing, on which the Serbian industry relies to a great extent. That's why Serbia is vulnerable because a large part of the IT sector is related to outsourcing and work for foreign clients, and this means that the consequences could "spill over" to Serbia if a client in the US or EU decides to optimize costs with the help of AI. It is notable that the global slowdown in investments has already left negative consequences[19]. For the above-mentioned reasons, in Serbia, this applies especially to the part of outsourcing services. It is this sector that is dependent on Western clients, primarily from the USA and the European Union, where the reduction of IT budgets has led to a drop in demand for these services. The results of the research indicate that as many as 74%

of respondents would leave or consider leaving the company, if mandatory attendance at the office was introduced, and that percentage is highest among millennials (29-44) and senior profiles. Also devastating is the fact that even 62% of companies did not change their salaries in the past 12 months, which also represents the most common drop in employee satisfaction.

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of the research show the difference in

the level of development of individual countries in the area of the IT sector and digital transformation. The European Commission published indicators of the progress of member states in the field of digital transformation as part of the Report on the State of the Digital Decade 2024. The comparison below is based on official data for 2024 published in national profiles for Serbia and the EU [5].

DESI 2024 KEY INDICATORS – SERBIA COMPARED TO THE EU			
Indicator (DESI 2024)	Serbia	EU Average	EU 2030 Target
Very high capacity network (VHCN) coverage	72.0 %	78.8 %	100 %
FTTP (fibre to the premises) coverage	66.5 %	64.0 %	100 %
5G coverage	58.0 %	89.3 %	100 %
SMEs with at least basic digital intensity	43.0 %	57.7 %	90 %
Use of cloud services	31.0 %	38.9 %	75 %
Use of artificial intelligence	6.5 %	8.0 %	75 %
Use of data analytics	18.0 %	33.2 %	75 %
Individuals with basic digital skills	51.0 %	55.6 %	80 %
ICT specialists as a percentage of total employment	4.0 %	4.8 %	-10 %
Digital public services for citizens	70.0 %	79.4 %	100 %
Digital public services for businesses	74.0 %	85.4 %	100 %
Access to electronic health records	81.0 %	79.1 %	100 %

Source: Western Balkans DESI 2024 (European Commission) and Digital Agenda Serbia – 2024

Fig. 2: Comparison of the state of IT in Serbia and the EU [5]

The data shows that the number of active companies in the IT sector of the Republic of Serbia with annual revenues of at least one million dinars is over 5,000. In the last eight years, the IT sector in the Republic of Serbia has recorded a real growth of an incredible 193 percent, and the next sector in terms of growth is professional and scientific services with 93.5 percent. Research shows that Serbia has a share of 5G coverage in rural areas (58%) compared to the EU average of 89%. Serbia also stands out with over 66.5% FTTP coverage in urban centers, enabling a higher quality of service in commercial centers and industrial zones. An important indicator according to the report is the use of cloud solutions in small and medium-sized enterprises. Compared to the EU average with 38.9%, Serbia is below the average with 31%, which indicates a more cautious approach to data transfer in the cloud. As for the companies themselves, 32,362 companies and entrepreneurs are registered in Serbia under the code Computer programming, of which 12,955 are active, and 7,722 are temporarily suspended. According to the report, companies in Serbia have a digital intensity (51.7%), the use of data analytics (18%), while the use of artificial intelligence (6.5%), which is below the European average of 8.0%. In terms of the type of IT activity, computer programming is the most represented, with as many as 22,411 economic entities, while consulting services are in second place, with 4,901 economic entities. The data also indicate that Serbia achieves 70% of digital public services for citizens and 74% for businesses, which is below the EU value. In addition, Serbia exceeds the EU average in electronic health services (81.0% versus 79.1% in the EU). The analysis of the IT sector in the environment showed that this is one of the fastest growing fields of the economy with a total growth of 72% in the last five years. In addition to the above, Serbia has a smaller share of the population with basic digital skills (51%) than the EU (55.6%). This remains one of Serbia's greatest compar-

ative weaknesses — despite evident technological progress, its population lags behind in the knowledge and use of digital tools. When looking at the structure of companies that operate under the computer programming activity code, micro-enterprises are overwhelmingly dominant - as much as 87%. Small enterprises occupy 11%, medium enterprises 1.3%, while only 0.25% belong to large enterprises. In terms of the region, Belgrade absolutely dominates in terms of the number of registered IT companies and entrepreneurs, with 17,224, i.e. 47.8 percent of the entire market in the Republic of Serbia. Also based on the previous geographical observation, the largest number of IT companies is from the Belgrade area (49.06%), and within the capital, Novi Beograd (12.25%), Stari Grad (9.10%) and Vračar (4.60%) are leading the way. The share of ICT experts in Serbia (4.0%) is also lower than the European average (4.8%). Among other things, the aforementioned research shows that Serbia lags behind in the use of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence with (6.5%) compared to the EU average of 8.0%.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The research results show that technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) and data analytics are gaining momentum in the IT sector as well, where companies from Serbia are increasingly collaborating with global partners. Based on the research, the conclusion is that the strategic plan of each individual company should serve as the primary guide for the selection of IT projects. Research shows that aligning IT projects with explicit business goals is a key reason why companies decide to invest in them. The results in practice show that considering that the starting salaries of junior programmers in Serbia reach €1,000-1,500, while experienced experts earn up to €5,000, investing in IT education can be one of the most profitable decisions for people looking for a well-paid job. The education system still represents one of the key obstacles for the further development of the IT sector,

because it is not fully aligned with the needs of the market. According to data reported by Business Insider, about 41 percent of companies plan to reduce the number of employees due to the application of AI technologies. In this context, according to the research, the most affected will be employees at junior and "mid" levels. However, despite the above, the data shows that between 65,000 and 75,000 specialists are currently working in the IT sector of Serbia, and there are no official data on layoffs due to AI yet. The growth in the export of software solutions and IT services shows that the IT sector still has the potential to be a key driver of economic development in the country. It can be concluded that the IT market in Serbia has a certain resilience because labor costs in Serbia are lower than in the West, so the economic calculation of layoffs is less aggressive than, for example, in more developed Western countries. Based on the above, it can be concluded that the rapid development of technology creates an increasing need for experts, and that the education system must fully follow these changes. In this regard, the conclusion is that the state of the IT sector in Serbia will go in the direction of gradual consolidation and the pressure on salaries and the growth of the demand for AI skills, and those who do not adapt will be at the greatest risk, we emphasize this because the IT sector in Serbia has a structural advantage - relatively is young, flexible and used to quick adaptations. Despite the challenges, the IT sector is one of the few that shows resilience and adaptability, even in periods of economic instability. The application of artificial intelligence and machine learning is becoming more pronounced, and domestic companies are increasingly working on projects that use these technologies to improve business processes, data analysis and interaction with users. Some less positive predictions indicate that in the coming years, manual programmers will eventually and exclusively be hired for some critical software, of which there is not even 2%, for everything else, AI will write 95% of the code in a maximum of 3 years... of course still with human supervision. In other words, it boils down to the fact that AI will do 90+% of IT things, and the rest will be narrowly specialized companies for dedicated solutions and problems. The forecast is that the application of AI in programming and its implication with which it will be possible to reproduce or make a better system with much less human resources, and therefore significantly reduce the need for human resources. In this context, in the future it will no longer be important the number of programmers a country has, but how many of them know how to work with the help of artificial intelligence

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